

IDEMBRU “Identification of emerging *Brucella* species: new threats for human and animals”

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JRP17 - IDEMBRU

WP	WP leader	WP deputy leader	Other involved partners
1	INIAV – AC Ferreira	NDRVMI–BFSA– H Daskalov	ANSES, APHA, BfR, FLI, IZSAM
2	INSA – A Pelerito	BfR – S Al Dahouk	ANSES
3	APHA - R. Ashford	IZSAM – G. Garofolo	ANSES, BfR, FLI, INIAV, INSA , WBVR
4	FLI – F Melzer	BfR – S Al Dahouk	ANSES, APHA, IZSAM, INIAV, INSA
5	WBVR – A Umanets	Anses – L Freddi	APHA, BfR, FLI, IZSAM
6	IZSAM – F. De Massis	APHA – A. Whatmore	All partners involved
7	Anses – C Ponsart	INIAV – AC Ferreira	

WP 2 - Recording the situation of brucellosis in human

- WP 2 Task 2.1 Implemented a network of laboratory surveillance of brucellosis and elaboration of a epidemiological questionnaire;
- WP 2 Task 2.2 - Isolation and detection of *Brucella* spp.
- WP 3 Task 2.3 Analysis data and constitutions of biobank

WP2 – T1 Dissemination of the network by all hospitals, and others in the country alerting the eventual emergence of new species of Brucella;

Institutions	Region
• National Hospitals	All
• Private laboratories	All
• Directorate General of Health	All
• Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Lusofona	Lisbon region
• Slaughters of Setubal	South of Contry

WP 2 - T 2 - Isolation and detection of Brucella spp.

Source /Type	Number samples	Isolation	Realtime PCR	Serology	WGS
National Hospitals - Blood	53	Not done	All negative	All negative	Not done
National Hospitals – LCR	25	Not done	1 <i>Brucella melitensis</i>	Not done	Not done
National Hospitals – strains	6	6 <i>B. melitensis</i>	Positive for IS711 / BME		<i>B. melitensis</i>
National Hospitals - biopsy	10	1 <i>B. intermedia</i> 1 <i>B. melitensis</i> 8 negative	Positive for IS711 Positive for IS711 / BME 8 negative	Not done	<i>B. Intermedia</i> <i>B. melitensis</i>
Reference Laboratory - serum	200	Not done	7 Positive IS711	5 positive	No results
DogBReeders	15	Not done	All negative	All negative	Not done

WP3 - Genomic characterisation of Brucella detected from samples and selected isolates

- Task 2. Harmonisation and standardisation of protocols for whole genome sequencing

- • Tissue Qiamp (Qiagen)
- • Kingfisher (Thermofisher)
- • ZYMO Research – DNA Miniprep Kit

WP3 - Genomic characterisation of *Brucella* detected from samples and selected isolates

- Task 3. Whole genome Sequencing

- • MiSeq Illumina platform (Illumina Inc.)
- • dual-indexed Nextera XT Illumina library preparation
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- • INNUca v3.1 pipeline
- • Extraction in silico MLVA and wgMLST

Ana Pelerito ,Alexandra Nunes ,Maria Sofia Nuncio ,João Paulo Gomes. Genome-scale approach to study the genetic relatedness among *Brucella melitensis* strains. 2020. Plos One.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0229863>

WP3 - Genomic characterisation of *Brucella* detected from samples and selected isolates

Phylogenetic tree with representative genomes of several *Brucella* species
(*B. microti*, *B. canis*, *B. suis*, *B. ceti*, *B. ovis*, *B. melitensis*, *B. abortus*, *B. anthropi* and *B. intermedia*)

WP3 - Genomic characterisation of Brucella detected from samples and selected isolates

Phylogenetic tree only with *B. intermedia* and *B. anthropi* genomes

WP3 - Genomic characterisation of Brucella detected from samples and selected isolates

ATB Resistance

GENE	PRODUCT	RESISTANCE	%COVERAGE	%IDENTITY
cmI_Ochro	Cml family chloramphenicol efflux MFS transporter	CHLORAMPHENICOL	97.91	84
blaOCH-7	class C extended-spectrum beta-lactamase OCH-7	beta-lactams	99.49	82.88

Virulence factors

GENE	PRODUCT	%COVERAGE	%IDENTITY
htrB	(htrB) lipid A biosynthesis lauroyl acyltransferase [LPS (CVF383)] [Brucella melitensis bv. 1 str. 16M]	100	86.91
acpXL	(acpXL) acyl carrier protein [LPS (CVF383)] [Brucella melitensis bv. 1 str. 16M]	100	93.26
fabZ	(fabZ) (3R)-hydroxymyristoyl ACP dehydratase [LPS (CVF383)] [Brucella melitensis bv. 1 str. 16M]	100	82.38
kdsA	(kdsA) 2-dehydro-3-deoxyphosphooctonate aldolase [LPS (CVF383)] [Brucella melitensis bv. 1 str. 16M]	100	81.89
ricA	(ricA) Rab2 interacting conserved protein A [RicA (VF0414)] [Brucella melitensis bv. 1 str. 16M]	100	80.87
wbpZ	(wbpZ) mannosyltransferase C [LPS (CVF383)] [Brucella melitensis bv. 1 str. 16M]	98.94	89.66
manAoAg	(manAoAg) mannose-6-phosphate isomerase [LPS (VF0367)] [Brucella melitensis bv. 1 str. 16M]	100	90.55
manCoAg	(manCoAg) mannose-1-phosphate guanylyltransferase [LPS (VF0367)] [Brucella melitensis bv. 1 str. 16M]	83.72	90.53
kdsB	(kdsB) 3-deoxy-manno-octulosonate cytidyltransferase [LPS (CVF383)] [Brucella melitensis bv. 1 str. 16M]	81.76	84.99
pgm	(pgm) phosphoglucomutase [LPS (VF0367)] [Brucella melitensis bv. 1 str. 16M]	100	86.01
cgs	(cgs) cyclic beta 1-2 glucan synthetase [C<beta>G (VF0366)] [Brucella melitensis bv. 1 str. 16M]	99.48	86.12
acpXL	(acpXL) acyl carrier protein [LPS (CVF383)] [Brucella melitensis bv. 1 str. 16M]	99.16	96.6

WP4 - Phenotypic characterisation of *Brucella* detected from samples and selected isolates

Task 2 - Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EMERGE project partner)

- 56 samples *Brucella spp.* tested
- BMD tests were performed with user-defined commercial microdilution plates (MICRONAUT, MERLIN Diagnostika, Berlin, Germany)

WP4 - Phenotypic characterisation of Brucella detected from samples and selected isolates

Strain	Species	Geographic origin	Biological Product	Host	Biovar	RAM_MIC	DOX_MIC	TET_MIC	GEN_MIC	STR_MIC	CMP_MIC	LEV_MIC	T/S_MIC	CIP_MIC
120/99E	B. melitensis	Cordoba	Sangue	Humana	1	0,5	0,25	<0,016	1	2	2	0,25	0,016/0,2	>4
167/00E	B. melitensis	Cordoba	sangue	Humana	1	0,38	0,125	0,032	1	1	2	0,125	0,016/0,2	2
194/00E	B. melitensis	Cordoba	Sangue	Humana	1	0,5	0,064	0,023	1	0,5	2	0,5	0,016/0,2	0,25
457/06E	B. melitensis	A Coruna	Sangue	Humana	2	0,5	0,125	0,032	1	2	2	0,125	0,016/0,2	0,25
213/03E	B. melitensis	Teruel	Sangue	Humana	1	0,38	0,047	<0,016	1	2	2	0,125	0,031/0,5	0,25
170/04E	B. melitensis	Valencia	Sangue	Humana	2	0,5	0,19	0,047	1	1	2	0,25	0,25/4,76	2
238/04E	B. melitensis	Teruel	Sangue	Humana	2	0,75	0,125	0,047	2	2	2	0,25	0,25/4,76	2
723/07E	B. melitensis	Burgos	Liquido arti	Humana	2	0,75	0,094	0,023	1	1	2	0,25	0,25/4,76	2
104-11RK	B. melitensis	Germany	Desconheci	Desconhe	3	1,5	0,5	0,19	1	4	2	0,25	0,25/4,76	2
104-12 RK	B. melitensis	Germany	Desconheci	Desconhe	3	1,5	0,19	0,25	2	4	2	0,25	0,25/4,76	2
104-13RK	B. melitensis	Germany	Desconheci	Desconhe	3	1	0,38	0,074	1	4	2	0,25	0,25/4,76	2
183-4RK	B. melitensis	Hungary	Desconheci	Desconhe	3	2	4	2	1	4	2	0,25	0,25/4,76	2
183-6RK	B. suis	Hungary	Desconheci	Desconhe	2	0,75	0,75	0,125	1	2	2	0,25	0,25/4,76	0,25
183-7RK	B. ovis	Hungary	Desconheci	Desconhe	2	1	0,19	0,094	2	1	2	0,25	0,25/4,76	0,25
148-9RK	B. melitensis	Belgium	Desconheci	Desconhe	3	12	1,5	0,38	1	1	2	0,25	0,25/4,76	0,25
146-10RK	B. melitensis	Spain	Desconheci	Desconhe	3	2	1	1,5	1	1	2	0,25	0,25/4,76	0,25
146-11RK	B. abortus	Spain	Desconheci	Desconhe	2	1,5	0,38	-	1	4	2	0,25	0,25/4,76	0,5
146-12RK	B. melitensis	Spain	Desconheci	Desconhe	3	1,5	0,5	0,19	2	2	2	0,25	0,25/4,76	0,5

WP4 - Phenotypic characterisation of Brucella detected from samples and selected isolates

Strain	Species	Geographic		Biological		Biovar	RAM_MIC	DOX_MIC	TET_MIC	GEN_MIC	STR_MIC	CMP_MIC	LEV_MIC	T/S_MIC	CIP_MIC
		origin	Product	Host	Product										
1P	B. melitensis	Portuguesa	Estirpe	Humana		2	1	0,023		2	2	2	0,25	0,031/0,5	0,5
35P	B. melitensis	Portuguesa	Estirpe	Humana		2	>32	0,19		1	1	2	0,25	0,25/4,76	0,5
36P	B. melitensis	Portuguesa	Estirpe	Humana		2	1	0,19		1	1	1	0,125	0,031/0,5	0,5
38P	B. melitensis	Portuguesa	Estirpe	Humana		2	0,5	1,5		1	1	1	0,5	0,031/0,5	0,5
40P	B. melitensis	Portuguesa	Estirpe	Humana		1	2	0,047		1	1	1	0,25	0,031/0,5	0,5
41P	B. melitensis	Portuguesa	Estirpe	Humana		2	0,75	0,19		2	1	1	0,25	0,016/0,2	0,25
43P	B. melitensis	Portuguesa	Estirpe	Humana		2	1,5	0,125	0,032	2	1	1	0,25	0,016/0,2	0,25
44P	B. melitensis	Portuguesa	Estirpe	Humana		2	1,5	0,094		1	1	2	0,25	0,016/0,2	0,25
66 P(127624)	B. melitensis	Portuguesa	Estirpe	Humana		2	1,5	0,19		2	4	2	0,25	0,016/0,2	0,25
71P	B. melitensis	Portuguesa	Estirpe	Humana		3	1,5	0,094		1	1	2	0,125	0,016/0,2	0,25
147P	B. melitensis	Portuguesa	Estirpe	Humana		1	1,5	0,25	0,094	2	4	4	0,5	0,016/0,2	0,25
153P	B. melitensis	Portuguesa	Estirpe	Humana		1				1	2	2	1	0,016/0,2	0,25
165P	B. melitensis	Portuguesa	Estirpe	Humana		3	>32	0,125		2	2	1	0,25	0,016/0,2	0,25
166P (SP)	B. melitensis	Portuguesa	Estirpe	Humana		2	2	<0,016		2	2	2	0,25	0,016/0,2	0,25
167P (XX)	B. melitensis	Portuguesa	Estirpe	Humana		2	1,5	0,023		2	2	4	0,25	0,016/0,2	0,25
168 P(2)	B. melitensis	Portuguesa	Estirpe	Humana		2	2	0,19		1	1	2	0,25	0,031/0,5	0,25
187P	B. melitensis	Portuguesa	Estirpe	Humana		3	0,19	1,5	0,032	2	4	2	0,25	0,25/4,76	0,25
194P	B. melitensis	Portuguesa	Estirpe	Humana		2	0,19	0,125	0,047	1	2	1	0,125	8/152	1
209P	B. melitensis	Portuguesa	Estirpe	Humana		3	0,25	0,094	0,032	1	2	2	0,031	0,031/0,5	0,031/0,5
228P	B. melitensis	Portuguesa	Estirpe	Humana		3	1,5	0,125	0,032	2	4	2	0,25	0,031/0,5	2
234P	B. melitensis	Portuguesa	Estirpe	Humana		3	1	0,19	0,032	1	2	2	0,25	0,031/0,5	0,016
240P	B. melitensis	Portuguesa	Estirpe	Humana		3	0,5	0,19	0,032	1	2	2	0,25	16/304	1
258P	B. melitensis	Portuguesa	Estirpe	Humana		3	0,5	<0,016	0,094	1	2	2	0,031	0,031/0,5	1
261P	B. melitensis	Portuguesa	Estirpe	Humana		3	0,5	<0,016	0,094	1	2	2	0,25	0,031/0,5	1

Planned Activities

- ◆ Research the Brucella in Fishermans;
- ◆ Research the Brucella in workers of the Slaughters
- ◆ Development of a decision-tree as a tool to support decision-making concerning emergent *Brucella* species infections

Publications

- Pelerito, A., *et al.* (2021). **Genetic characterization of *Brucella* spp: whole genome sequencing – based approach for determination of Multiple Locus Variable Number Tandem Repeat profiles.** *Front. Microbiol.* 12:740068. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2021.740068
- Tscherne A, Mantel E, Boskani T, Budniak S, Elschner M, Fasanella A, Feruglio SL, Galante D, Giske CG, Grunow R, Henczko J, Hinz C, Iwaniak W, Jacob D, Kedrak-Jablonska A, Jensen VK, Johansen TB, Kahlmeter G, Manzulli V, Matuschek E, Melzer F, Nuncio MS, Papaparaskevas J, Pelerito A, Solheim M, Thomann S, Tsakris A, Wahab T, Weiner M, Zoeller L, Zange S; EMERGE AST Working Group. (2022). **Adaptation of *Brucella melitensis* Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing to the ISO 20776 Standard and Validation of the Method.** *Microrganisms.* [10.3390/microorganisms10071470](https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms10071470)

Thank you very much!!!!!!

